

Workshop Summary:

How do we measure and communicate the value of urban nature?

26. juni 2025

Introduction

Urban nature is more than green spaces. It contributes to well-being, health, social cohesion, and resilience in the face of climate change. But how do we measure these values? How do we communicate them, and what role can digital tools play?

These questions formed the foundation of the workshop, which brought together participants from municipalities, digital actors, architects, landscape architects, consultants, businesses, interest organisations, universities, etc.

The purpose was to develop new perspectives and practical ideas for making the value of urban nature visible, measurable, and scalable. It also explored how digital tools can support the decisions and priorities that shape the development of nature in future buildings, cities, and urban environments.

The workshop was co-hosted by BLOXHUB and the City of Aarhus, both partners in the Horizon Europe project URBREATH. Aarhus also partners in the Horizon Europe project BIPED. Both projects aim to advance data-driven, inclusive, and resilient urban development across Europe.

See links:

urbreath.eu

bi-ped.eu

[BLOXHUB.org](https://bloxhub.org)

Workshop content

The workshop brought together expert insights and interactive discussions, creating a dynamic exchange of ideas.

Inspirational talks

- **The history of nature in Aarhus and insights into the Midtby Vision** / Anne Mette Boye, City Architect, Aarhus Municipality
- **Plans for Vesterbro Square: How do we create well-being and value through urban nature?** / Anne Hartvig Mogensen, Partner, LYTT Architecture
- **Digital solutions from URBREATH, Aarhus Municipality, and BIPED for measuring and communicating the value of urban nature** / Kristoffer Bringø, Architect, Department of Technology and Environment, Aarhus Municipality
- **Site-specific data and how we experience urban nature** / Taryn Cullen Humphrey, Architect, Gehl
- **From data to action: working with urban nature** / Laurids Sund, Co-Founder & CEO, Gismap

Interactive discussions

The workshop actively engaged participants to bring diverse perspectives into play, laying the groundwork for further work towards practical tools, measurement methods, and communication approaches to demonstrate the value of urban nature.

- **What role do partnerships play in advancing urban nature?**
- **How does nature create value in the city - and for whom?**
- **How can we measure and communicate the value of urban nature?**
 - Which concrete indicators can help measure and communicate this value?
 - Which (digital) tools or initiatives can support measurements and communicate this value - and how?
 - What systemic factors are at play if we are to create a new understanding of urban nature's value?
- **How can we engage key stakeholders in the development of urban nature?**
- **Key perspectives for continued exploration**

Why is urban nature essential?

Greening urban spaces plays a crucial role in creating healthy and attractive urban environments that enhance both physical and mental well-being while acting as a buffer against climate change.

Awareness of nature in construction is also critical - both in material choices and in preserving natural areas, where nature often competes with the built environment.

Nature and construction must become deeply integrated into our mindset.

What role do partnerships play in realising and strengthening urban nature?

Collaboration across sectors, disciplines, and levels of governance is crucial for a holistic approach and lasting impact. These partnerships must be bold and backed by funding.

Partnerships should start early. Perhaps partnerships should be reframed as “collaborations” to emphasise that they are something citizens can also participate in.

Inspirational talk

The history of nature in Aarhus and insights into the Midtby vision

/ Anne Mette Boye, City Architect, Aarhus Municipality

The changing role of nature in urban development

Humanity's relationship with nature has undergone profound changes over time. In the past, life was deeply connected to the landscape. This shifted during the industrial era, when nature was primarily regarded as a source of raw materials. Later, it came to be understood as a recreational resource, a place of refuge for people living in cities. In Aarhus, it is only within the past 15 years that natural processes have been actively integrated into urban development. The city is shaped by its landscape structures, from Brabrand Lake to the Aarhus River, and its natural waterways continue to play a defining role. Where it was once wet, water will still find its way.

Rethinking the city's typology

The Midtby Vision (City Centre Vision) challenges the traditional idea of the city as something separate from nature. It invited us to rethink what we mean by "city," "nature," and how these relate to the biological foundation of life.

By 2030, Aarhus is envisioned to consist of one-third city, one-third production, and one-third nature. This transformation involves reducing agricultural land from 60% to 30% and fundamentally rethinking how new nature can be designed and integrated into the city's structure.

Nature at different scales

The city's future form will incorporate nature on various scales, from the expansive bay landscape and striking valleys to city parks and down to intimate elements, such as flowerbeds and green pockets.

The vision aims to strike a balance between the desire for density in the city centre and the need for greening and climate adaptation. Green urban spaces should not only serve as decorative features but also function as active elements in the city's ecological cycles.

Plans for Vesterbro Square: How do we create well-being and value through urban nature

/ Anne Hartvig Mogensen, Partner, LYTT Architecture

Vision: From traffic space to blue-green urban space

Vesterbro Square in Aarhus is transforming a traffic-dominated space into a green, vibrant urban area, led by LYTT Architecture. Where the square once functioned as a parking island surrounded by eight roads, the ambition is now to create a cohesive square full of life and opportunities for social interaction. The project builds on the square's unique location at the meeting point between hill and valley. The city's elevation differences, which were once seen as a barrier, are now being utilised as an active element in the landscape design.

Water as a lever for new qualities

A key starting point for the project has been water management. Initially, the plan was to handle 300,000 litres of stormwater, but during the process, this volume was tripled to over one million litres. The square now functions more as a cloudburst corridor than as a local green sponge. This has expanded the project's geographical scope and created new opportunities to connect it with the city's surrounding blue and green structures, including the Botanical Garden, Mølleparken, and the Aarhus River.

A project in constant development

The scope and focus of the project have evolved significantly over time. What began as a relatively contained urban space transformation has grown to encompass extensive climate adaptation, green mobility, and blue-green infrastructure. This development has required the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders, including the fire department, water utility companies, infrastructure departments, and various municipal divisions. This collaboration has ensured that the square will not only become a green oasis but also a robust and functional part of the city's overall infrastructure.

An urban space based on citizen wishes

The project is rooted in a wide range of requests and input from citizens and local stakeholders. Many requested more greenery, fewer cars, and safer spaces for social interaction. The result will be an urban space with generous edge zones, bicycle parking, and bus stops, alongside dedicated areas for relaxation, play, and daily life. The square will also be able to host food stalls, markets, and communal dining, making it a flexible setting for both everyday activities and special events.

Data and digital tools as a basis for decision-making

A key part of the vision is the use of data and digital models as tools for understanding and shaping the city's development. Parameters such as air quality, biodiversity, and the number of cyclists are not only viewed as snapshots but as indicators of long-term urban quality and health. By incorporating this data into planning, Aarhus can develop into a city where nature and urban life coexist in a dynamic, mutually dependent relationship.

The future of nature in Aarhus

Aarhus Municipality is focused on how the city can, in the future, be understood as a balanced landscape. Through targeted integration of natural processes, a new distribution of land, and the use of digital decision-making tools, the foundation is being laid for a city that can handle future climate challenges while improving everyday life and health for its citizens.

Digital solutions from URBREATH, Aarhus Municipality and BIPED to measure and communicate the value of urban nature

/ Kristoffer Bringø, Architect, Department of Technology and Environment, Aarhus Municipality

A digital framework for green city development

Aarhus Municipality is systematically integrating nature's functions into urban development, with digital tools playing a central role. Through EU Horizon projects such as **URBREATH** and **BIPED**, as well as the municipality's own 3D city model, a strong data foundation is being established to support both short-term and long-term decision-making.

URBREATH (2024-2027) focuses on nature-based solutions and the development of digital tools. BIPED (2024-2026) focuses on developing Positive Energy Districts and supporting the city's green energy transition. Since 2016, the Aarhus has also used a 3D city model for communication, administration, and decision-making.

Together, these projects support Aarhus' ambition to become climate neutral by 2030 and enable data-driven, visual city management.

The many functions of nature

A key part of the work is understanding the broad value of nature. Digital tools can help make visible the many functions urban nature can serve in a city context, including nature as:

- A cooling element and buffer against heat islands
- A filter for air pollution
- A foundation for biodiversity and ecological connections
- A traffic-calming element and a source of noise reduction
- Support for stormwater management
- A contributor to the citizens' quality of life and the overall value of an area

Digital tools can visualise these functions step-by-step, creating a more holistic understanding of nature's contribution to the city.

Planting for identity and biodiversity

The choice of planting is driven by a desire to strengthen both biodiversity and the site's identity. Approximately 70 new trees will be planted in the city centre, while the existing plane trees will be preserved as a strong signal that the existing nature is valued.

The focus is on native species and plants that provide year-round flowering, nectar, and visual variety. Rain gardens, street plantings, and flowerbeds will capture and clean water while creating green pockets in the urban landscape.

Blue-green synergies

The project includes disconnecting downspouts, sealing off road drains, and filtering stormwater through special soil. More than 800 m² of former asphalt surface will be transformed into green areas. Basins planted with herbs and grasses will support the site's natural cycles.

A stepping stone for aarhus' future urban development

Vesterbro Square is seen as a catalyst for urban development in Aarhus. The project serves as an initial step in a broader movement that will gradually extend the city's green qualities toward the Ring Road. Monitoring the square's green development will be straightforward and operational, allowing for the application of lessons learned to future urban spaces and to inform discussions on the connection between green public spaces and the city's social and economic value creation.

[See presentation](#) →

Site-specific data: How we experience urban nature

/ Taryn Cullen Humphrey, Architect, Gehl

An experience-based approach to urban nature

Gehl works from the principle that we measure what we value. This philosophy underpins an interdisciplinary approach that combines observations of city life, physical spaces, and people's experiences. Nature is understood as an active co-creator of social connections and well-being, rather than just a green backdrop.

Eye Level City: A tool for subjective data collection

Gehl has developed the *Eye Level City* app to collect site-specific, experience-based data at eye level. Users take photos, annotate their experiences, and map movement patterns. The data is later processed in workshops where participants interpret and give meaning to the material themselves. This collective interpretation fosters a deeper understanding of how urban nature affects feelings of safety, belonging, and well-being, and reveals the diversity of perceptions regarding what constitutes "good" nature.

Insights from case studies

- **Charlotte (USA):** Data showed that a lack of nature and poor maintenance created insecurity. Well-lit, well-maintained natural spaces were associated with positive experiences, while proximity to traffic triggered discomfort and anxiety.
- **Nordhavn (Copenhagen):** When residents felt connected to nature, 88% reported a positive experience of the place. However, nature does not always generate joy. Poorly thriving vegetation or signs of pollution can create negative associations.
- **Stanford (USA):** The findings showed that tightly manicured natural areas can feel alienating and decorative rather than inviting. In contrast, informal, lush pockets of nature created strong feelings of closeness and belonging, offering inviting places for rest and quiet.

Nature as social infrastructure

Across cases, a recurring theme is the role of nature as part of the city's social infrastructure. Nature is experienced not only as a visual or climatic contribution but as a vital framework for making people feel welcome and engaged.

Visualisation as a dialogue and decision-making tool

Another key element is the use of visual data and 3D models to foster understanding and dialogue. Within URBREATH, the following digital solutions are being developed:

- **3D model** showing urban spaces and trees, developed by *Virtual City Systems*
- **Analysis of visual and physical access to trees**, including the use of the "3-30-300 rule" (being able to see three trees from home, 30% tree canopy cover, and a maximum of 300 meters to a park), developed by *VITO*
- **Network analysis tool** to assess distances to green areas, developed by *DEDA*

Aarhus Municipality utilises *Bentley OpenCities Planner*, which features 3D models that will eventually serve as a dialogue tool in public consultations and inform political decisions.

The ambition is to communicate complex data in a way that is easy to understand, both for professionals and citizens, providing a foundation for more inclusive urban development.

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From data to action in working with urban nature

/ Laurids Sund, Co-Founder & CEO, Gismap

Data as a driver of green transition

Gismap is a new digital platform that maps outdoor areas using an AI-based model. The model covers all Danish land parcels and combines public datasets, including high-resolution aerial imagery and elevation data. The platform provides a detailed picture of existing green structures and their potential in the city.

This data foundation creates a solid basis for planning and serves as an objective supplement to political and opinion-driven discussions.

Mapping green elements

The platform enables detailed identification and analysis of various land types, including asphalt, buildings, green roofs, natural grass, shrubs, forests, and water elements. A key tool in Gismap is the **biofactor**, which expresses an area's overall green quality and biodiversity.

The biofactor can track development over time and show the effects of specific initiatives. The platform can also document facade vegetation and create comparative baselines between city areas.

Scenario planning

An example from Marselisborgcentret in Aarhus illustrates the platform's potential. By adding more trees and forest, the biofactor could be increased from 0.59 to 1.07. This type of visualisation supports decision-making processes by clearly illustrating the impact of green initiatives before they are implemented. The platform thus serves as a tool for translating data into concrete, actionable plans.

Looking ahead

The plan is to expand the platform's functions to include social and economic parameters. This will enable the connection between the impact of green initiatives and factors such as property value growth and social benefits, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the importance of nature in urban development.

[See presentation](#) →

By combining citizens' experiential data with concrete design interventions, new opportunities arise to shape public spaces that support social interaction and mental well-being. Gehl's work with Eye Level City shows how site-specific, experience-based data can reveal nature's role and value in urban life, reframing nature as an active social actor rather than just a physical feature.

[See presentation](#) →

Interactive discussion

How does nature create value in the city - and for whom?

Participants explored the various ways of understanding the value of nature and which stakeholders and interests nature brings value to.

Group 1: The social perspective

The group highlighted nature's role as a universal common space. Nature offers openness, where access is not dependent on status, appearance or gender. At the same time, nature can also divide us, as urban residents have different preferences, from the neatly trimmed rose garden to the more informal, wild vegetation.

Nature also provides space for spontaneous encounters, where a conversation on a bench can arise naturally and without the social codes that often shape other solo activities in the city, such as dining out or going to the cinema alone. Despite its importance for human interaction, nature always exists on its own terms and without demanding anything in return.

Group 2: The health perspective

The group highlighted nature as a key factor in both physical and mental well-being. Improved air quality and reduced noise contribute directly to well-being and act as preventive health factors. Nature is increasingly integrated into the healthcare system's toolbox, both in addressing mental health and as a means of alleviating chronic illnesses.

From a socio-economic perspective, infrastructure such as cycle paths should be viewed not only as a means of transportation but also as an investment in reduced sick leave and improved quality of life. Even a green view from a hospital bed can promote healing and shorten recovery times. Strengthened natural quality also benefits other living organisms, supporting broader ecological health.

Group 3: The infrastructural perspective

The group emphasised the influence of nature on behaviour and mobility. The presence of green elements makes routes more attractive and can itself be a motivating factor for choosing a bicycle over a car. We are more inclined to cycle when the surroundings are shaped by nature, because we enjoy looking at greenery and find it beautiful and inviting.

It was also noted that nature can heighten drivers' awareness and serve as a protective buffer for other infrastructure. Nature can emerge in interaction with existing structures, for example, when old railway lines evolve into green corridors.

An example, such as the E45 motorway, illustrates that even extensive infrastructure facilities can contain and be surrounded by areas that support biodiversity. Nature was

thus presented as a dynamic part of infrastructure that can influence movement patterns and strengthen the city's green connectivity.

Group 4: The environmental and biodiversity perspective

This group stressed that ecosystems are closely linked to all other themes. Prioritising the environment and biodiversity not only benefits species and ecosystems but also strengthens social communities.

Children and people in rehabilitation were highlighted as vulnerable groups that particularly benefit from healthy natural areas and lower pollution and temperature levels. Environmental considerations and biodiversity can also prove valuable for investors in the long term, as green qualities are reflected in financial performance.

Group 5: The economic and climate perspective

The group focused on the economic value of nature, particularly in the real estate market, where green areas and certifications can position buildings as attractive investments. At the same time, questions were raised about how the financing of green initiatives should be distributed. Should it primarily be carried by municipalities and utility companies, or can private actors also play a larger role?

The group also highlighted risks associated with green investments, including the possibility that nature may become an exclusive resource accessible only to a limited group, and the danger of short-term solutions if assets are not managed strategically and with a long-term perspective.

Summary:

The participant dialogues made it clear that the value of nature in the city is complex and multidimensional. Nature is not just a green feature, but an active contributor to social interaction, health promotion, infrastructure, biodiversity and the economy. At the same time, it raises important questions about fair access and long-term responsibility.

Overall, the discussions suggest a need to reevaluate the role of nature as an integral part of both urban development and the fundamental structures of society.

Café dialogues: How can we measure and communicate the value of urban nature?

Participants engaged in a café-style process, rotating between questions and building on each other's reflections.

Café dialogue: Which concrete indicators can help measure and describe the value of urban nature?

Participants emphasised that indicators and data are essential for assessing the value of nature, while acknowledging that data alone does not represent the objective truth. It must be linked to *who* we are measuring and *what* the purpose of the measurement is.

Indicators should include both qualitative and quantitative data, such as:

- **Experience:** Sense of safety, perceived value of the area, perceived aesthetics and value of it, and recognition of the site's history
- **Usage:** How is it used (activities), by whom (user group), and for what is it used (purpose). Registrations of changes in usage throughout the year. Number of visitors and duration of stay.
- **Health:** Changes in disease patterns, number of sick days, and changes in exposure to daylight. Level of air and noise pollution. Convenience and availability of active transportation (number of bike parking spots, bike lanes, and traffic data)
- **Air quality:** e.g., CO₂ and gas levels
- **Biodiversity and species:** Number and diversity of species, Biofactor (BAF)
- **Temperature:** Temperature variations (differences between green areas and concrete)
- **Climate:** Trees' CO₂ absorption, soil quality, water management
- **Urban bio score/Biofactor:** Habitats, percentage of greenery in the area, number of trees, tree health, origin of plant material
- **Points in DGNB:** Biodiversity strategy, including current status and clear targets
- **Diversity and inclusion:** Users' economic background and demographics, accessibility for people with disabilities (quantity and type of accessible facilities/features), safety measurements (quantity & type of lighting, mobility safety precautions) and time spent in the area (as social surveillance)
- **Mobility patterns:** Before and after changes
- **Land use:** Size of natural spaces, appropriateness of scale for use by people and other species
- **Behaviour:** Changes in movement patterns and reciprocity (giving back to nature)

Café dialogue: Which (digital) tools or initiatives can support measuring and communicating the value of urban nature – and how?

The choice of tools was highlighted as an important strategic decision. Each measurement instrument involves both inclusion and exclusion, thereby setting a direction for what we prioritise in our understanding of nature. It is about striking a balance between our view of the past, our present needs, and our future goals. Key points from the dialogue included:

- Develop a **baseline**, set clear goals, and monitor progress over time
- Include **technological solutions** for planning, monitoring and evaluating (e.g., sensors)
- Combine **technological solutions** with **human observations**
- Develop a type of **LCA measurements** for natural elements
- Need for **communication tools** to support nature engagement and awareness, and convey data and value to different target groups.
- **Social media** can support dissemination and public engagement
- Tools should be able to measure both **qualitative and quantitative values**
- Create **future scenarios** aligned with desired outcomes
- Identify how to ask the right questions and measure the right things (leading back to *who* we are measuring and *what* the purpose of the measurement is)

Café dialogue: Which systemic factors are at play if we are to create a new understanding of urban nature's value?

The dialogue emphasised that a changed understanding of nature requires a systemic perspective involving citizens, private actors and public institutions. Nature should not only be present but also made visible and part of everyday conversations.

Examples such as visible rain gardens, signs explaining local species, or information about the amount of air pollution a tree helps reduce were highlighted as concrete ways to raise awareness. The goal is to increase awareness among all stakeholders so that we move from asking "What does nature give us?" to instead asking "What can we give back to nature?"

Within municipalities, there is a need for collaboration across departments, as nature can be integrated into areas such as mobility, climate, health and more. Working across departments can also make it easier to secure funding for projects that promote nature.

Economy and financing were top priorities in the dialogue about nature in cities. This requires a focus on the business case for nature, both in the short and long term, so that the long-term value of nature in cities is also taken into account.

Nature can help reduce social inequality in cities, for example, through the public housing sector, which often has a mixed resident composition. The public sector often has the will but not the means, and increased collaboration with municipalities and private actors could help meet this challenge. There is a need to create shared responsibility across sectors, including public, private and civil society, where citizens can also be involved and gain ownership, for example, through participatory activities like "come help plant with us"

Finally, it was suggested that long-term change should also be reflected in legislation. The presence of nature can be incorporated through requirements in public tenders, ensuring that new projects actively incorporate green qualities rather than adding them as an afterthought.

Summary

This part of the group work showed that measuring the value of nature cannot be reduced to a technical question. It requires a fundamental shift in mindset and involvement across sectors. By increasing visibility and commitment to nature in both daily life and legislation, we can move toward urban development where the value of nature becomes an integrated and essential part of decision-making.

How can we engage key stakeholders in the development of urban nature?

Participants formulated ideas on how to build understanding and engagement around the value of urban nature among key stakeholder groups, as well as how different actors can contribute to strengthening nature in the city.

Developers

It was highlighted that developers often express green ambitions, but these risk ending up as content in an annual sustainability report rather than leading to real change. The group highlighted the potential of presenting investments in nature as a visible contribution to reputation building and as a tangible way to enhance a building's identity and market value.

At the same time, it was noted that green solutions can be the most economically advantageous in the long term. Examples such as the difference between maintaining gravel and a planted ground cover over time illustrate how nature can be both a more beautiful and cost-effective solution.

Citizens

For citizens, it was suggested to activate playful and sensory formats that make engagement fun and easy. Examples like nature bingo, treasure hunts, and walk-and-talks can create new relationships with green spaces and communicate the potential of nature in an accessible way.

There was an emphasis on involving existing groups and platforms to create anchoring and continuity, allowing engagement to grow organically and on the citizens' own terms.

Politicians

The group discussed how nature is often politicised to attract specific voter groups, such as families with children. A key point was the need for politicians to experience nature directly and get out of their offices.

Citizens were also highlighted as potential spokespersons for nature, especially if they are informed about current legislative processes and can time their messages strategically. As a symbolic point, it was proposed that nature could have "a seat on the city council" to make it clear when its voice is not being heard.

Urban planners

Planners play a central role in integrating traffic, operations and nature management, but often feel they carry a heavy responsibility alone. There was a call for better political frameworks, such as clear requirements for nature in planning legislation or specific guidelines for tree protection in municipal plans.

It was emphasised that progressive initiatives and data should be made more accessible to inspire peers more broadly. At the same time, there is a need for overarching regional coordination, similar to what previously existed at the county level, to ensure coherence in the landscape perspective.

Cross-sector collaboration

It was noted that taking the first steps requires courage, both for startups and municipalities, when it comes to new digital solutions and nature projects. It was proposed to establish spaces where municipalities and entrepreneurs can co-develop and test solutions, possibly in collaboration with national associations, economists and the business sector.

A shared development space can strengthen both innovation and risk willingness, while also ensuring that new solutions receive organisational and political support.

Summary:

The discussions revealed that engagement in nature development necessitates tailored approaches for each stakeholder group and a shared focus on visibility and anchorage. By combining playful citizen activities, clear political frameworks, economic incentives, and strong collaborative spaces, the value of nature can be promoted as a shared concern, benefiting both people and urban ecosystems.

Key perspectives for further exploration

As a conclusion to the workshop, all participants contributed ideas on themes that could be explored further. These topics may inspire future activities to support urban nature among the participants.

1.

Future nature partnerships

How can we ensure that collaborations receive the financial and organisational support they need? For example, by examining concrete models for governance, roles and responsibilities in partnerships that can lead to long-term investments in urban nature.

2.

Balancing wild and maintained nature types in dense urban areas

How do we navigate between different types of nature, considering both biodiversity, user experience and safety? This requires a discussion of ecological functions and social dimensions within a unified urban ecosystem.

3.

Connecting quantitative data and human experiences as a basis for better decisions

Both qualitative and quantitative data points are essential. We can explore how best to integrate and weigh different types of data in decision-making processes.

4.

The risk of green gentrification and access to nature

The increasing value of natural areas can contribute to inequality and create groups without access to these areas. How can we ensure that investments in nature and development do not only benefit the most privileged? This opens up a discussion on regulation, financing and design strategies that prioritise inclusion.

5.

The economic value of nature and its integration into urban economic models

It is worth examining how the value of nature, both direct and indirect, can be more clearly incorporated into economic decisions and investments. For example, how biodiversity, health and recreational values can increasingly become part of business cases, market analyses and municipal budgets.

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